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D3.2

Use Case Data Management Plans

WP3
Community, Support and Use Cases

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D3.2 – Use Case Data Management Plans

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Executive Summary

This document describes the data management strategy for the four BioExcel-2 Use Cases that are already described in the concurrent deliverable D3.1 - Use Case Work Plans, namely:

Use Case 1: Antibody Design

Use Case 2: High-throughput Modelling of Interactomes

Use Case 3: Rational Drug Design

Use Case 4: Electronic Interaction Phenomena

The general data management principles and strategy are described, and detailed data management plans are given for data that is expected to be produced as part of the Use Cases. These include how the data will be stored and made findable and accessible, and preserved for future use beyond the lifespan of the current project

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Introduction

The BioExcel Centre of Excellence is committed to open data following FAIR principles, participates in the Open Research Data Pilot¹, and aims to facilitate long-term data archival. This will be achieved with tools to facilitate metadata harvesting and deposition and, as a general policy that is applicable to the data produced as part of the four BioExcel-2 Use Cases, by storing relevant data in open repositories such as Zenodo or, where data size exceeds limits on repository size, in institutional repositories, possibly linked to global or federated ones such as OpenAire². Examples of this strategy include planned HADDOCK extensions to facilitate deposition of structural models in the Protein Data Bank (PDB) hosted jointly by EMBL-EBI and the storage of Molecular Dynamics trajectories in databases that facilitate reproducibility and re-use of simulation results for analysis such as BigNASim/MoDEL.

This document describes the Data Management Plans (DMPs) for the BioExcel-2 Use Cases (UCs), which constitute the primary activities within BioExcel-2 that are expected to generate research data, and which are therefore clearly in scope of the Open Research Data Pilot. The Use Case data management plans are structured in a similar way to a DMP for research projects, with the caveat that the UCs are not projects *per se* but rather research activities aimed at showcasing BioExcel capabilities in the context of real-world challenges. UCs are expected to evolve in response to user and community needs as well as project-internal software and workflow developments and will be reviewed on a 12-month basis. As such, the DMP will be reviewed in accordance with this. A full description of each Use Case can already be found in the concurrent deliverable D3.1 - Use Case Work Plans.

The template for the Use Case DMPs, which is given in the following section, is based on the DMP template for the UK's Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC)³. The plans are formulated to contain enough information to ensure that data and metadata from the work undertaken will be Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR⁴). Each Use Case aims to address the points and questions in the Data Management Plan template.

¹ <https://www.openaire.eu/what-is-the-open-research-data-pilot>

² <https://www.openaire.eu>

³ https://dmponline.dcc.ac.uk/template_export/1407052318.pdf

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>

Data Management Plan Template

Use Case data management plans were formulated following the below template.

Data Collection

What data will be collected/created - distinguish between raw and processed/curated data? How much data is expected to be collected/created?

Are there common data types e.g. experimental data, modeling data, etc?

How will data be collected/created?

Documentation and Metadata

What documentation and metadata will accompany the data?

Ethics and Legal Compliance

How will you manage any ethical issues?

How will you manage copyright and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) issues?

Storage and Backup

How will the data be stored and backed up during the research?

How will you manage access and security?

Selection and Preservation

Which data are of long-term value and should be retained, shared, and/or preserved?

What is the long-term preservation plan for the dataset?

Data/Metadata Access and Sharing

How will you (or others) access the data?

What is the policy for sharing data incl. publication?

Are any restrictions on data sharing required?

Responsibilities and Resources

Who will be responsible for data management?

What resources will you require to deliver your plan?

Use Case 1: Antibody design

Description

One of the fastest growing branches in the pharmaceutical industry is drug design based on antibodies, with antibody (Ab) fragments already proving to be an important class of therapeutics, overtaking small molecule drugs from synthetic chemistry. These macromolecular pharmaceuticals give extremely high specificity and the ability to use the body's own immune system to eliminate diseased tissue e.g. tumors, but their computational design is challenging due to their size and complexity.

Key challenges are:

- to reliably predict 3D structures of antibodies, in particular the Complementarity-Determining Regions (CDRs)
- to model their binding mode and understand how structure and dynamics are altered in this process
- to predict improved binding affinity through systematic amino acid mutations

This Use Case aims to address all these challenges through an integrative approach combining the core BioExcel software comprising of GROMACS, HADDOCK and PMX, and with the development of computational workflows to facilitate usability and execution on Exascale high-performance computing resources.

Data Collection

The data used in this use case are coming from open and public database like the Protein Data Bank [1], providing access to experimental structures and other databases such as SKEMPI [2] collecting binding affinity changes upon mutations. Furthermore, the binding affinity changes for antibody-antigen complexes are collected in the publicly available databases: ATLAS [3] and AB-BIND [4].

Structural data are typically following the well-defined PDB [5] or mmCIF [6] formats.

[1] <http://www.pdb.org>

[2] <https://life.bsc.es/pid/skempi2/>

[3] <http://atlas.wenglab.org/web/index.php>

[4] <https://github.com/sarahsirin/AB-Bind-Database>

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[5] <http://www.wwpdb.org/documentation/file-format>

[6] <http://mmcif.wwpdb.org>

The various software used in Use Case 1 will generate a variety of data (e.g. coordinate / trajectory files) in relevant formats as is found to be useful as the Use Case work develops.

Documentation and Metadata

Structural data stored in PDB or mmCIF format will follow the proper respective definitions.

Any other simulation data generated by this use case will include a README file in each sub-directory describing the content of the data.

The simulation protocols and parameters used for alchemical free energy calculations with pmx and molecular dynamics simulations with GROMACS will be described in the corresponding parts of scientific publications. The protocols and simulation parameters together with versioning information for the software used will be deposited in a publicly accessible repository.

Ethics and Legal Compliance

N.A.

Storage and Backup

Data will be stored on local servers during the research.

Data are not sensitive. No special measures required beyond standard authenticated access procedures for local & remote systems.

Selection and Preservation

Setup and analysis scripts, together with the relevant (depends on the software) generated data will be stored and shared, ideally through open repositories. The preserved data and metadata should allow third parties to repeat the computations with proper settings and compare the newly obtained results with the deposited data i.e. to ensure reproducibility.

The long-term preservation plans are as follows:

- For HADDOCK, datasets associated with a publication are usually deposited in the SBGrid data repository (<https://data.sbgrid.org/labs/32/>) with an associated DOI.

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- For GROMACS: We will use long term storage facilities at the PDC - Center for High Performance Computing at KTH
- For pmx: After the completion of Use Case 1, the alchemical free energy calculation data will be placed on a long term archive server at MPG.

Data/Metadata Access and Sharing

Data and metadata will be made available through open repositories such as Zenodo or, where data size exceeds limits on repository size, in institutional repositories, possibly linked to global or federated ones such as OpenAire.

For any cases where the raw data produced by the alchemical free energy calculations and molecular dynamics simulations exceeds the limit imposed by Zenodo or institutional repositories, such raw data will be available upon request from the relevant Use Case partner.

No restrictions on data sharing are required unless proprietary industry data is used, in which case access will be limited to project partners and will not be made public.

Responsibilities and Resources

Responsible partners for data management are:

HADDOCK: Alexandre Bonvin (UU)

GROMACS: Christian Blau and Alessandra Villa (KTH)

pmx: Vytautas Gapsys and Bert de Groot (MPG)

No resources are expected to be needed beyond those already available

Use Case 2: High-throughput Modelling of Interactomes

Description

The human genome has revealed over 20,000 expressed proteins, known as the proteome, which are the workhorses of human life and perform all manner of critical cellular functions. These proteins, however, do not work in isolation, but by interaction with each other and with other biomolecules, thereby forming a complex network of interactions known as the interactome. This intricate network consists of all interactions involving hundreds of thousands of protein-protein and other biomolecular complexes. Irregularities in the functioning of the interactome, e.g. through environment-induced miscommunication or mutation-induced alterations to the proteome are responsible for many diseases, which is why it is important to understand how the interactome works at the atomic level.

There are two main challenges associated with understanding the interactome:

Adding the structural dimension to possibly hundreds of thousands of interactions between protein-protein and other biomolecular complexes
Predicting what the interactome (the network) looks like given the knowledge of the proteome (the building blocks of the network), which requires predicting the affinity of the complexes involved

The first challenge will require running massive amounts of independent docking runs in parallel, all generating large numbers of files. The second challenge will require all-vs-all docking of the network components and prediction of their binding affinity, e.g. using parallel molecular dynamics simulation. Doing so in an efficient manner and achieving the Use Case goals will require efficient usage of high-throughput (HTC) and high-performance computing (HPC) including on Exascale resources, and efficiently handling and analysing large amounts of data.

Data Collection

The data used in this use case are coming from open and public database like the Protein Data Bank [1] providing access to experimental structures.

Structural data are typically following the well-defined PDB [2] or mmCIF [3] formats.

[1] <http://www.pdb.org>

[2] <http://www.wwpdb.org/documentation/file-format>

[3] <http://mmcif.wwpdb.org>

The various software used in Use Case 2 will generate a variety of data (e.g. coordinate / trajectory files) in relevant formats as is found to be useful as the Use Case work develops.

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Documentation and Metadata

Structural data stored in PDB or mmCIF format will follow the proper respective definitions.

Any other simulation data generated by this use case will include a README file in each sub-directory describing the content of the data.

Ethics and Legal Compliance

N.A.

Storage and Backup

Data will be stored on local servers during the research.

Data is not sensitive. No special measures are required beyond standard authenticated access procedures for local & remote systems.

Selection and Preservation

Setup and analysis scripts, together with the relevant (depends on the software) generated data will be stored and shared, ideally through open repositories. The preserved data should allow third parties to repeat the computations with proper settings and compare the newly obtained results with the deposited data

Long-term preservation plans are as follows:

- For HADDOCK, datasets associated with a publication are usually deposited in the SBGrid data repository (<https://data.sbgrid.org/labs/32>) with an associated DOI.
- For GROMACS: We will use long term storage facilities at the PDC - Center for High Performance Computing at KTH

Data/Metadata Access and Sharing

Data and metadata will be made available through open repositories such as Zenodo or, where data size exceeds limits on repository size, in institutional repositories, possibly linked to global or federated ones such as OpenAire.

For any cases where raw data exceeds the limit imposed by Zenodo or institutional repositories, such raw data will be available upon request from the relevant Use Case partner.

D3.2 – Use Case Data Management Plans

No restrictions on data sharing are required unless proprietary industry data is used, in which case access will be limited to project partners and will not be made public.

Responsibilities and Resources

Responsible partners for data management are:

HADDOCK: Alexandre Bonvin (UU)

GROMACS: Christian Blau and Alessandra Villa (KTH)

No resources expected to be needed beyond those already available

Use Case 3: Rational Drug Design

Description

Rational drug design is a methodology to design drug molecules that bind to a target (e.g. protein, nucleic acid). It relies on prior knowledge of the structure, function, and mechanism of the target, thereby avoiding random testing of thousands of molecules. The BioExcel Centre of Excellence will create a set of workflows related to rational drug design. These workflows will be connected to large scale high-performance computing (HPC) resources, using the expertise gained in the first period of the project. The usability of this set of workflows will be assessed by Nostrum Biodiscovery by running tests on systems with relevance to the pharmaceutical industry. Results of these tests, possibly done using massively parallel executions on the infrastructures of the Barcelona Supercomputing Center, will be stored and made available following the DMP described in this document.

Data Collection

Use case 3 involves many different application runs, which will generate a broad variety of data in many different formats. Table 1 summarises the types of data produced by the experiments, with the possible formats associated. Whenever possible, the generated data types will be formatted using standards in the field, such as the PDB [1] file format for 3D macromolecular structures, SDF/MOL2 for small molecules or XTC file format for MD trajectories (this latter is specifically related to GROMACS package).

[1] <http://www.wwpdb.org/documentation/file-format>

Table 1. Data types and formats produced by the different experiments in use case 3

Experiment	Type	Format
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Structure modeling MD setup Protein ligand docking Trajectory clustering	Macromolecule 3D Structure	PDB MOL MOL2 SDF GRO
MD simulation	Simulation trajectory	XTC
Ligand parameterization Free Energy Perturbation	Small compound force-field parameters	GROMACS ITP GROMACS TOP
Macromolecular flexibility	Time series plots	DAT XVG
Essential Dynamics (Principal Component Analysis - PCA)	Time series plots Compressed Trajectory	DAT XVG PCZ
Pathological Mutation Prediction	Protein SNV/SAV pathological report	ASCII Text CSV JSON
Classical Molecular Interaction Potentials	3D grid representing molecular properties	GRD CUBE

Data description:

- **Macromolecular 3D Structures:** Experimental or theoretical models of structural macromolecules obtained from public databases (PDB, DUD-e, DrugBank, Protein Model Portal, etc.) or from modeling, docking and simulation methods.
- **Simulation Trajectories:** Trajectories and metadata for molecular dynamics trajectories of macromolecules
- **Ligand Parameters:** Force-field parameters associated to small compounds, needed to run MD simulations or FEP of ligands or protein-ligand complexes.
- **Macromolecular Flexibility Analysis:** Results of flexibility analysis done on macromolecular structures and simulation trajectories.
- **Essential Dynamics:** Results of principal component analysis done on simulation trajectories, extracting the correlated motions of proteins which are the most fundamental to the activity of the protein.

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- **Pathological Mutation Prediction:** Results of a pathological mutation prediction from a trained classifier using sequence conservation and physico-chemical properties (PMut).
- **Classical Molecular Interaction Potentials:** Results of a classical molecular interaction potential (CMIP).

Documentation and Metadata

For macromolecular 3D structures, data will follow Protein Data Bank (PDB) recommendations and formats for documentation and metadata. Simulation metadata and molecule description for simulation trajectories will follow data ontologies as described in EDAM ontology and in [[Ten simple rules on how to create open access and reproducible molecular simulations of biological systems](#)]. Ligand parameters and macromolecular flexibility analysis (including essential dynamics) documentation and metadata will follow data and formats terms as described in EDAM ontology (Missing EDAM terms would be eventually proposed to EDAM maintainers). Pathological mutation predictions documentation and metadata will be included in the generated JSON files. Classical Molecular Interaction Potentials data will be accompanied by a documentation file with information about the content of the grid.

Ethics and Legal Compliance

Data generated during all the phases of use case 3 will be stored for publication. No personal or sensitive data is expected.

Storage and Backup

Data storage and backup will be provided by the IRB Barcelona--BSC long -term archive file systems and databases, through the [Starlife](#) infrastructure. Access and security are coupled to the research center's user's credentials.

Selection and Preservation

Molecular dynamics trajectories used to extract relevant information for the use case will be stored and made available following the simple rules from [[Ten simple rules on how to create open access and reproducible molecular simulations of biological systems](#)], allowing the reproduction of the trajectories from the input configuration files. Reduced trajectories containing an ensemble of snapshots representing the full dynamics of the system, as well as a complete set of flexibility analysis, will be stored in the IRB Barcelona--BSC long -term archives, and made available through a new IRB MD database similar to e.g. [MoDEL](#) and [BigNASim](#) that is currently being developed. Similarly, results coming from Docking experiments or ligand parameterizations will be stored in the IRB Barcelona/BSC long-term archives and made available through IRB databases.

Data/Metadata Access and Sharing

Data will be made available through open databases (IRB) or repositories (zenodo), with a proper FAIR identifier or DOI. Local database identifiers will be communicated through the identifier.org service. Data will be stored for publication.

Responsibilities and Resources

BSC and IRB partners will manage all data, using the resources provided by the institutions.

Use Case 4: Electronic Interaction Phenomena

Description

This use case focuses on modeling complex cases that go beyond what is possible with classical methods and employ QM/MM calculations that combine the GROMACS and CP2K engines for two test applications: investigation about the impact of proton dynamics in ESI/IM-MS experiments, and a study of fluorescent proteins in fluorescence spectrometry.

Data Collection

The data that will be collected are molecular dynamics trajectories. These trajectories are generated by numerically solving Newton's equations of motion for a molecular system on high-performance computing resources, e.g. at CSC, PRACE. These trajectories store energies, pressure, temperature, atomic positions, atomic velocities, atomic forces of a many atom system, as a function of simulation time in a compressed binary format. The portable XDR routines are used to read and write these binary files.

Documentation and Metadata

The trajectory data consist of the popular portable XDR format and can thus be accessed on multiple computing platforms. The simulations models, consisting of simulation parameters (timestep, methods for computing interactions, etc), starting structures, topologies (i.e. the interactions) force field files and QM/MM models, are stored as ASCII text. The format of these files follows the Gromacs and CP2K standards. All new algorithms that will be developed and used in the Use-Case will be coded in the C++ (.cpp) or Python (*.py) languages and made publicly available as part of the open-source Gromacs molecular dynamics program that is distributed under LGPL (www.gromacs.org)

Ethics and Legal Compliance

Because the data generated in this project does not concern people, there are no ethical issues.

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Because molecular dynamics program GROMACS (www.gromacs.org) is released under the lesser GNU public license (LGPL), all co-developers, including ourselves, are copyright holders of the new simulation code that we will develop. In Finland, based on the Act on the Right in Inventions made at Higher Education Institutions, the university owns the rights to inventions. The university takes care of the IPR protection measures and costs (such as patenting) when the university owns the rights to research results.

Storage and Backup

The trajectories can be generated again provided the input parameters, structures and force field model are all available. Therefore, we securely store the latter data on the university's backup systems. We will also make all input required to reproduce our trajectories and results, as well as source codes publicly available at www.gromacs.org or www.virtualchemistry.org.

Selection and Preservation

Because we expect to generate in total well over a TB of molecular dynamics trajectories, it will be technically difficult to share these trajectories directly with others. Instead, we will make all that is needed to reproduce these trajectories on any high-performance computing system publicly available, including starting structures, force fields, simulation parameter and source codes.

Data/Metadata Access and Sharing

The trajectories will be analyzed and the result of these analyses will be published in scientific journals. Because of high amounts of data generated, we will instead provide users with the input files needed to reproduce our results will be made publicly available. These will be stored in a publicly accessible repository such as Zenodo or JYX digital archive (jyx.jyu.fi). Publications will include a link to the repository with the data used.

Responsibilities and Resources

JYU will manage all data. The published part of research data will be made accessible in compliance with the principles of open science, using desired terms and conditions of use. For the distribution and publication of research data, the University's own platforms (JYX digital archive: jyx.jyu.fi) and backup storage will be used.